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EFFECTS OF ELECTRO MAGNETIC DAMPING SUSPENSION ON VEHICLE DYNAMICS AND PASSENGER'S COMFORT

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Abstract:

Vehicle Dynamics is a criteria which is mostly affect two things- Passenger Comfort and Vehicle Control. These two things causes major design changes in today's suspension systems. There is no system which is truly ideal for both the conditions. But usage of active suspensions systems can reduce the compromises done in the system. The objective of this project is to undermine a new product launch in market which will serve the masses one of the best technologies available in market with a new thinking process and innovative ideas.

The technology is priced at high cost but this innovative project will cater the masses costing at lesser price besides advances in the market. And by far the most unique technology is of electromagnetic suspending systems. This technology can truly prove to be ideal for both the scenarios, in real world time. EMDS is an original design study, which is based on the principle electro magnetic levitation which works as an mother working principle.

Key Words: Electromagnetic suspension, vehicle dynamics, safety, Innovation and Electromagnetic damping (EMD)

1.Introduction

Modern world represents more problems and obstacles and to overcome these obstacles with convention design structure and schematics for more than a decade we rely on old designs and there iterated versions suited for different designs. EMDS can face exactly any obstacle and hindrances through in its way. Due to use of magnetic field in the design we can alter any situation in its favor. Magnetic resonance occur in this situation can be programmed to make it use as an active system and also as passive system. Vibrations run in a vehicle while in its operation can cause a major problem in suspension dynamics. It can induce variant support of unsprung mass with variation of sprung mass. This can prove to be fatal especially in case of an OFF-ROAD buggy. We require performance at its best in such rough terrains, a millimetre difference can choose to be fatal for the vehicle as well as the driver.

Magnetic flux generated by electromagnets can be altered with a programmed control unit such as an E.C.U. while the driver adjusts the vehicle according to the terrain the suspension can tune itself for the required adjustments both for the vehicle as well as the terrain.

A magneto rheological damper or magneto rheological shock absorber is a damper filled with MR fluid, which is controlled by a magnetic field, usually using an electromagnet. This allows the damping characteristics of the shock absorber to be continuously controlled by varying the power of the electromagnet. This type of shock absorber has several applications, most notably in semi active suspension which may adapt to road conditions, as they are monitored through sensors in the vehicle. This technology is relatively excellent in its array of work. But it comes with a huge cost investment required from the consumer. Whereas using electromagnets can prove to be less costlier than using MR fluid. By Adjusting the coil emf, we can enable the system to support required mass. One of the primary goals of a suspension system is to isolate road vibrations and resonated frequencies, developed by the vehicle while in motion, and isolate it from the passengers compartment. MR damper has pneumatic linkage to transfer such shocks through un filtered, whereas an EMDS is having virtual no linkages apart from solid mounting points to transfer the load which results in absolutely nil vibrations and a smooth ride for the passengers.

2.Objectives

The main objective of this paper is to propose elimination of compromises made in conventional systems and suggest alternative with a cheap, reliable and innovative source of damping. The objective of this project is also to develop novel car suspension systems to improve the passenger's comfort and safety so a special material was chosen to make an important device in the suspension system. The study also carries out detailed exploratory study about the Magneto Rheological (MR) fluid comprises a fluid that is able to turn solid nearly instantly when brought near a magnet. When the magnet is taken away it completely reverts back to liquid. This controllable change of state with some desirable features such as high strength, good stability, broad operational temperature range, and fast response time show great potential in automobile application adding to passenger's safety and vehicular control.

3.Literature Review

Magnetic levitation is a very old technology which is used all across the world in things such as Magnetic levitated trains but Electro magnetic levitation is a technology which is untouched till date and there is no progress going over it. So, we have taken this part as applying it in the suspension system of the vehicle and developing it keeping in mind about the dynamics of a vehicle for advanced passenger's comfort and ride quality.

Review of suspension system

H. F. Lam, et al of the Department of Mechanical and Automation Engineering, The Chinese University of Hong Kong have done a project on Automobile Suspension Systems with MR Fluid Dampers and have told that the ride quality is concerned with the sensual or feel of the passenger in the environment of a moving vehicle. Vibrations in today's high speed vehicles including automobiles severely affects their ride comfort and safety. To improve the ride comfort, effective vibration control of suspension systems is increasingly necessary.

Bart L. J. Gysen, Member, IEEE, et al have done a research project on Active Electromagnetic Suspension System for Improved Vehicle Dynamics. According to this the paper offers motivations for an electromagnetic active suspension system that provides both additional stability and manoeuvrability by performing active roll and pitch control during cornering and braking, as well as eliminating road irregularities, hence increasing both vehicle and passenger safety and drive comfort. Various technologies are compared with the proposed electromagnetic suspension system that uses a tubular permanent-magnet actuator (TPMA) with a passive spring. Based on on-road measurements and results from the literature, several specifications for the design of an electromagnetic suspension system are derived. The measured on-road movement of the passive suspension system is reproduced by electromagnetic actuation on a quarter car setup, proving the dynamic capabilities of an electromagnetic suspension system.

Magneto-Rheological Dampers for Super-sport Motorcycle Applications done by John W. Gravatt, Masters of Science In Mechanical Engineering, Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University which says that in recent years, a flurry of interest has been shown for a relatively old technology called magneto-rheological fluids, or MR fluids. Multiple types of devices have been designed to implement this versatile fluid, including linear dampers, clutches, work-piece fixtures, and polishing machines. The devices have been used in automobiles, washing machines, bicycles, prosthetic limbs, and even smart structures.

In 1980, Dr. Bose conducted a mathematical study to determine the optimum possible performance of an automotive suspension, ignoring the limitations of any existing suspension hardware. The result of this 5-year study indicated that it was possible to achieve performance that was a large step above anything available. After evaluating conventional and variable spring/damper systems as well as hydraulic approaches, it was determined that none had the combination of speed, strength, and efficiency that is necessary to provide the desired results. The study led to electromagnetic as the one approach that could realize the desired suspension characteristics. The Bose suspension required significant advancements in four key disciplines: linear electromagnetic motors, power amplifiers, control algorithms, and computation speed. Bose took on the challenge of the first three

disciplines, and bet on developments that industry would make on the fourth item. Prototypes of the Bose suspension have been installed in standard production vehicles. These research vehicles have been tested on a wide variety of roads, on tracks, and on durability courses.

4.Limitations Of Existing System

- Compromises riding handling characteristics.
- Excessive weight adds to sprung mass.
- Can be damaged very easily.
- Cannot control resonance between fore and aft body.
- Cannot be programmed according to each and every road situations.
- It can be optimized for one situation only

5.SUSPENSION SYSTEMS

5.1.BASICS

The automobile frame and body are mounted on the front and rear axle not directly but through the springs and shock absorbers. The assembly of parts, which perform the isolation of parts from the road shocks, may be in the forms of bounce, pitch and roll is called suspension system. Functions of suspension system:

- It prevents the vehicle body and frame from road shocks.
- It gives stability of the vehicle.
- It safeguards the passengers and goods from road shocks.
- It gives the good road holding while driving, cornering and braking.
- It gives cushioning effect.
- It provides comfort.

Fig. 3.1 Suspension components (Courtesy: HyDynamics Parts)

5.2 Attributes Of Suspension System

Conventional suspension system comprises of a army of components. Basically it has minimum two mounting flanges or clamps which is mounted - one on wheel upright or A-arms, and the other is mounted on the vehicular

frame, chassis or the body. Both of these are a solid mounting points which do not move or deform during operation. Other components are springs, damper body, piston arm assembly, orifice bore, seals etc.

Springs

Suspension systems are designed to travel with the wheel assembly as the vehicle encounters abnormal road conditions. Springs accomplish a portion of this task by providing a cushion for road impacts. All suspension systems incorporate some type of spring. While the spring design may vary, its main task remains the same. Damping Spring's accomplish one of the two major tasks of the suspension system - they absorb bumps or jounces caused by varying road surfaces. Shock absorbers are used to accomplish the other task - to control the rebound of the springs. Without damping, also known as dampening, the actions of the spring devices would not be controlled.

Spring Design

Springs are designed to have deflection rate and recoil frequency. A spring's deflection rate is the amount of bend that is induced with different weights. The rate is usually expressed as pounds needed to compress the spring one inch. A spring's recoil frequency is the time it takes to recoil or deflect in the opposite direction. Load does not affect frequency. The frequency depends on the spring's length, thickness and width.

Coil Springs

Coil springs are made of spring steel; the rods are formed to provide the appropriate compression strength and spring rate. They can be designed to handle a wide range of loads and have increased strength under higher loads. In some cases coil springs are mounted on the control arm, with the frame riding on top; in other cases they are mounted on struts, as part of a shock absorber and coil assembly. When mounted on a shock, the top is bolted to the chassis and held in place by a spring seat containing a rubber isolator.

Air Springs

Another type of spring is the air spring. The air spring is composed of an external air bladder, that when pressurized, provides vehicle support. The air spring is mounted between an axle or control arm and the vehicle's chassis and is either manually or automatically pressurized, depending on system design. Air springs are often used as supplemental spring force when carrying heavier loads with standard suspension systems.

Fig. 5.1. Air Suspension on Volvo 310

6.ELECTRO MAGNETIC DAMPING SUSPENSION (EMD) ON DOUBLE WISHBONE

This consists of two transverse links (control arms) either side of the vehicle, which are mounted to rotate on the frame, suspension sub frame or body and, in the case of the front axle, are connected on the outside to the steering knuckle or swivel heads via ball joints. The greater the effective distance c between the transverse links, the smaller the forces in the suspension control arms and their mountings become, i.e. component deformation is smaller and wheel control more precise. The main advantages of the double wishbone suspension are its kinematic possibilities.

Fig 6.1. Double Wishbone

The positions of the suspension control arms relative to one another can determine both the height of the body roll centre and the pitch pole. of the compressing and rebounding wheels, i.e. the change of camber and, irrespective of this, to a certain extent also the track width change. With shorter upper suspension control arms the compressing wheels go into negative camber and the rebounding wheels into positive. This counteracts the change of camber caused by the roll pitch of the body.

ROLL CENTER

The body roll centre is the point in the vertical plane which passes through the wheel centre points, and in which transverse forces (y-direction) can be exerted on the sprung mass, in other words the body, without kinematic roll angles occurring. The body roll centre is therefore the point in the centre of the vehicle (from the front), and in the centre of the axle (when viewed from the side), around which the body begins to roll when a lateral force acts, and at which reaction forces are absorbed between axle and body. Based on the existing track alteration curve of a wheel, the body roll centre is the point in the centre of the vehicle, which is intersected by a vertical, drawn on the tangent laid on the alteration curve in the centre of tire contact.

Fig: 6.2 Roll centre

ROLL AXIS

The position of the roll centers at the front and back and the course of the direction line joining these - the roll axis is of decisive importance for the handling properties. The height of the roll centers determines both the wheel load differences of an axle and hence the self-steering properties of the vehicle through the tire properties. As well as the necessary roll suspension, which is again crucial to comfort in the case of unilateral deflection where a high level of roll rigidity is required and a stabilizer is used. The position of the roll centre also depends on the instantaneous position of the wheel links, i.e. the roll centre usually only lies in the centre plane of the vehicle if there is symmetrical wheel displacement and alters its position both horizontally and as vertically with unilateral displacement (cornering), resulting in the unwanted support effects of the wheel link forces on the body.

Fig 6.3. Roll Axis

CAMBER

Camber is the angle between the wheel centre plane and a vertical to the plane of the road. It is positive if the wheel is inclined outwards and negative, when inclined inwards. When a vehicle is loaded with two or three persons a slightly positive camber would be useful on passenger cars to make the tires roll as upright as possible on the slightly transverse-curved road surface and give more even wear and lower rolling resistance.

Fig 6.4. Camber Angles

KINEMATIC CAMBER ALTERATIONS

One disadvantage of independent wheel suspension is that the wheels incline with the body on a bend, i.e. the wheel on the outside of the bend goes into positive camber relative to the ground, and the lateral grip of the tire under the greatest load (unlike the one on the inside of the bend) reduces. To balance this out, manufacturers tend to design the suspension on passenger cars such that the wheels go into negative camber as they travel in bump and into positive camber as they rebound.

Kinematic shift of camber while vehicle operations is magnified while in a off road track. One of the most important reason for this is sprung mass shifts during operation which plays with CG location placements.

Due to this camber changes kinematic in a double wishbone setup.

Fig. 6.5. Kinematic change of Camber

TOE SETTINGS

The static toe-in angle is the angle that results in a standing vehicle (reference status), between the vehicle centre plane in the longitudinal direction and the line intersecting the centre plane of one left or right wheel with the road plane. It is positive, when the front part of the wheel is turned towards the vehicle longitudinal centre plane and negative ('toe-out') when it is turned away.

The total toe-in angle is obtained by adding the toe-in angle of the right and left wheels. The total value is sometimes still given in millimeters. The toe-in is then the dimensional difference, by which the rim flanges at the back are further apart than at the front. The toe-in should be measured at the height of the wheel centre, when the vehicle is empty, with the wheels pointing straight forward; therefore relates to both wheels of one axle. Expressed in degrees, the toe-in angle of a wheel corresponds to the tire slip angle i.e. where there is toe-in, the front wheels of a vehicle are set to slip (drift).

Figure 6.6: Toe setting

7. ACTIVE SUSPENSION SYSTEM

- The active suspension and adaptive suspension/semi-active suspension are types of automotive suspension that controls the vertical movement of the wheels relative to the chassis or vehicle body with an onboard system, rather than in passive suspensions where the movement is being determined entirely by the road surface. Active suspensions can be generally divided into two main classes: pure active suspensions and adaptive/semi-active suspensions. While adaptive suspensions only vary shock absorber firmness to match changing road or dynamic conditions, active suspensions uses some type of actuator to literally raise and lower the chassis independently at each wheel.
- These technologies allow car manufacturers to achieve a greater degree of ride quality and car handling by keeping the tires perpendicular to the road in corners, allowing better traction and control. An onboard computer detects body movement from sensors throughout the vehicle and, using data calculated by opportune control techniques, controls the action of the active and semi-active suspensions. The system virtually eliminates body roll and pitch variation in many driving situations including cornering, accelerating, and braking.
- Active suspensions, the first to be introduced, use separate actuators which can exert an independent force on the suspension to improve the riding characteristics. The drawbacks of this design (at least today) are high cost, added complication/mass of the apparatus, and the need for rather frequent maintenance on some implementations. Maintenance can be problematic, since only a factory-authorized dealer will have the tools and mechanics with knowledge of the system, and some problems can be difficult to diagnose. Michelin's Active Wheel incorporates an in-wheel electrical suspension motor that controls torque distribution, traction, turning maneuvers, pitch, roll and suspension damping for that wheel, in addition to an in wheel electronic traction motor.

HYDRAULIC SUSPENSION

- Hydraulically actuated suspensions are controlled with the use of hydraulic servo mechanism. The hydraulic pressure to the servos is supplied by a high pressure radial piston hydraulic pump. Sensors continually monitor body movement and vehicle ride level, constantly supplying the computer with new data. As the computer receives and processes data, it operates the hydraulic servos, mounted beside each wheel. Almost instantly, the servo-regulated suspension generates counter forces to body lean, dive, and squat during driving maneuvers.
- In practice, the system has always incorporated the desirable self leveling suspension and height adjustable suspension features, with the latter now tied to vehicle speed for improved aerodynamic performance, as the vehicle lowers itself at high speed.
- Computer Active Technology Suspension (CATS) co-ordinates the best possible balance between ride quality and handling by analyzing road conditions and making up to 3,000 adjustments every second to the suspension settings via electronically controlled dampers.

8. ELECTROMAGNETIC RECUPERATIVE

- This type of active suspension uses linear electromagnetic motors attached to each wheel. It provides extremely fast response, and allows regeneration of power consumed, by using the motors as generators. This nearly surmounts the issues of slow response times and high power consumption of hydraulic systems. Electronically controlled active suspension system (ECASS) technology was patented by the University of Texas Center for Electro mechanics in the 1990s and has been developed by L-3 Electronic Systems for use on military vehicles. The ECASS-equipped HMMWV exceeded the performance specifications for all performance evaluations in terms of absorbed power to the vehicle operator, stability and handling. The Bose company has a proof of concept model as shown. The

founder of Bose has been working on exotic suspensions for many years while he worked as an MIT professor.

SEMI ACTIVE SUSPENSION

- Adaptive/semi-active systems can only change the viscous damping coefficient of the shock absorbers, and do not add energy to the suspension system. Though limited in their intervention (for example, the control force can never have different direction than the current vector of velocity of the suspension), semi-active suspensions are less expensive to design and consume far less energy. In recent times, research in semi-active suspensions has continued to advance with respect to their capabilities, narrowing the gap between semi-active and fully active suspension systems.

SOLENOID VALVE ACTUATED

- This type is the most economic and basic type of semi-active suspensions. They consist of a solenoid valve which alters the flow of the hydraulic medium inside the shock absorbers, therefore changing the damping characteristics of the suspension setup. The solenoids are wired to the controlling computer, which sends them commands depending on the control algorithm (usually the so-called "Sky-Hook" technique). This type of system used in Cadillac's Computer Command Ride (CCR) suspension system.

MAGNETO RHEOLOGICAL DAMPER

- Another fairly recent method incorporates magneto rheological dampers with a brand name MagneRide. It was initially developed by Delphi Corporation for GM and was standard, as many other new technologies, for Cadillac Seville STS (from model 2002), and on some other GM models from 2003.

Fig.8.1 Magneto Rheological Damper

- This was an upgrade for semi-active systems ("automatic road-sensing suspensions") used in upscale GM vehicles for decades. It allows, together with faster modern computers, changing the stiffness of all wheel suspensions independently. These dampers are finding increased usage in the US and already leases to some foreign brands, mostly in more expensive vehicles.

- In this system, being in development for 25 years, the damper fluid contains metallic particles. Through the onboard computer, the dampers compliance characteristics are controlled by an electromagnet. All the above options specified are typical in its setup and application but for a mass production view neither of these options are cheap and viable. We can find these technologies in vehicles from Lamborghini, Audi, Porsche, Ferrari etc. All of which are high end production car manufacturers. Essentially, increasing the current flow into the damper raises the compression/rebound rates, while a decrease softens the effect of the dampers. Information from wheel sensors (about suspension extension), steering, acceleration sensors and some others is used to calculate the optimized stiffness. The fast reaction of the system allows, for instance, make softer passing by a single wheel over a bump in the road. The proposed product EMDS can reform the market as it is as viable as Macpherson strut setup, and as reliable as any conventional systems available.

FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

In mathematics, the finite element method (FEM) is a numerical technique for finding approximate solutions to boundary value problems for partial differential equations. It uses the variation method (the calculus of variations) to minimize an error function and produce a stable solution. Analogous to the idea that connecting many tiny straight lines can approximate a larger circle, FEM encompasses all the methods for connecting many simple element equations over many small sub domains, named finite elements, to approximate a more complex equation over a larger domain. Hence the analysis was done for grid independence results, factor of safety results and displacement results on the chambers. Finite element analysis (FEA) has become commonplace in recent years, and is now the basis of a multibillion dollar per year industry. Numerical solutions to even very complicated stress problems can now be obtained routinely using FEA, and the method is so important that even introductory treatments of Mechanics of Materials such as these modules should outline its principal features.

In spite of the great power of FEA, the disadvantages of computer solutions must be kept in mind when using this and similar methods: they do not necessarily reveal how the stresses are influenced by important problem variables such as material properties and geometrical features, and errors in input data can produce wildly incorrect results that may be overlooked by the analyst. Perhaps the most important function of theoretical modelling is that of sharpening the designer's intuition; users of finite element codes should plan their strategy toward this end, supplementing the computer simulation with as much closed-form and experimental analysis as possible. Finite element codes are less complicated than many of the word processing and spreadsheet packages found on modern microcomputers. Nevertheless, they are complex enough that most users do not find it effective to program their own code. A number of prewritten commercial codes are available, representing a broad price range and compatible with machines from microcomputers to supercomputers. However, users with specialized needs should not necessarily shy away from code development, and may find the code sources available in such texts as that by Zienkiewicz² to be a useful starting point. Most finite element software is written in Fortran, but some newer codes such as ABAQUS are in C or other more modern programming languages. In practice, a finite element analysis usually consists of three principal steps:

9. COST ANALYSIS FOR EMDS

The production cost per damper is approximated to be roughly around thirty five thousand rupees which is very competitive than a conventional MR damper. The motive here is to cater the masses with a product rich in high end features and low on cost.

Phase II	Cost (INR)
MATERIAL	3320
MACHINING	5000
TESTING	10000
MARKET RESPONSE	5000
FUTURE ADVANCEMENTS	5000

10. CONCLUSION

An automobile's main concept is to transport goods and people over distances; otherwise there would be no use for them. Steering and braking have seen tremendous development for the masses at cheaper price, but comfort and luxury have seen to be forgotten and this field requires a new focus and that is what we have been working on. We chose active suspension for a reason, keeping in mind the comfort of passengers, not only for the rich, but something that could be provided to the vehicles for the masses. Vehicle Dynamics is a criteria which is mostly affected by two things- Passenger Comfort and Vehicle Control. These two things causes major design changes in today's suspension systems. There is no system which is truly ideal for both the conditions. But usage of active suspensions systems can reduce the compromises done in the system. And by far the most unique technology is of electromagnetic suspending systems. This technology can truly prove to be ideal for both the scenarios, in real world time. One of the similar technology is Magnetic Rheological fluid which works on the principle of charged iron particles scattered across a enamel solvent which when charged repels each other with equal charge storage capacity. But the only problem or shortcoming of such a damping solution is it is very costly and it is a semi active type suspension. What we are doing is similar to magnetic levitation devices but here with the help of multiple compression chambers we can achieve characteristics of a damper as well as a conventional spring setup.

This type of damper is a complete new technology, so there is a lot of room for the improvement of the system. Also, the damper can be fixed in any type of vehicle just by changing the size of the damper as because of that the size of solenoid changes which controls the pre-load and the damping. This type of damper will be extremely useful for off-road due to its versatility

REFERENCES

- Haiping Du, Kam Yim Sze, James Lam; Design of Semi Active control of vehicle suspension systems using Magneto Rheological Damping Prototype subjected to cyclic excitation; Journal of Sound and Vibration Pattern Analysis; PP - 305 - 431.
- K Kim, D Jeon, 1999, Journal of Intelligent Material Systems Vibration suppression in an MR fluid damper suspension system; University of Seoul, South Korea.
- M Gobbi, G Mastinu, 2001 Sound and Vibrational Analysis and optimization of the dynamic behavior of passively suspended road vehicles; Vibrational and Road Analysis International Conference; 7th Edition; PP-101-006.
- R Rajamani, 2011, Vehicle dynamics and control, trade-offs between Ride quality, rattle space achieved by Active System Parameters; Theoretical Journal of Suspension Model; PP - 141 - 143.
- Taylor and Francis, 1987 Road vehicle suspension system Design, Modeling and Road Surface Analysis for vehicles and performance criteria, derived from active suspension system control laws; Volume 1 Issue 9; PP-423-113.